

ZULFIYAXONIM SHE'RIYATIDA OBRAZLAR TIZIMI IFODASI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o'zbek shoirasi Zulfiyaxonim Isroilovaning hayot yo'li, she'rlarining mavzu ko'lami haqida tahlil olib borilgan. Shuningdek, shoira Zulfiyaning poetik asar yaratish mahorati uning she'rlari miqyosida ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Zulfiyaning hayot yo'li, tarjimalari, mukofot laureati, "Zulfiya" nomidagi davlat mukofoti.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется жизненный путь узбекской поэтессы Зульфияханым Исраиловой и масштаб ее стихов. Также на примере ее стихов рассмотрено умение поэтессы Зульфии создать поэтическое произведение.

Ключевые слова: жизненный путь Зульфии, переводы, лауреат премии, государственная премия имени «Зульфия».

Abstract. This article analyzes the life path of the Uzbek poetess Zulfiyakhanim Israilova and the scope of her poems. Also, poetess Zulfia's ability to create a poetic work was considered in terms of her poems.

Key words: Zulfia's life path, translations, award laureate, state award named after "Zulfiya".

"Zulfiya" taxallusi ostida ijod qilgan o'zbek shoirasi Zulfiyaxonim Isroilova 1915-yil bahorning ilk kuni bo'lmish, 1- martda Toshkent shahrida Isroil temirchi oilasida tavallud topgan.

Zukko shoira dastlab 1922-yildan 1931- yilgacha maktabda ,1931-1934- yillar oralig'ida qizlar bilim yurtida tahsil olgan.

Jurnalist va nashriyotchi bo'lgan o'zbek shoirasi 1935-1938- yillar mobaynida til va adabiyot instituti aspiranti, 1938- 1948- yillarda bolalar nashriyoti muharriri, O'zbekiston davlat nashriyoti bo'lim mudiri, 1953- yilgacha "Saodat" jurnalida bo'lim mudiri, 1953- 1980- yillarda shu jurnal bosh muharriri lavozimlarida ishlagan.

Zulfiyaxonim, taniqli o'zbek adibi Hamid Olimjon bilan 1935- yilda turmush qurgan.

Ammo ular orzularga to'la hayot kechirayotgan bir vaqtda taqdirning shafqatsizligi tufayli 1944- yilda Hamid Olimjon baxtsiz hodisa avto halokat tufayli hayotdan ko'z yumdi.

O'zbek she'riyatiga ulkan hissa qo'shgan shoiraning ilk she'ri 1931- yil "Ishchi" gazetasida, 1932- yil " Hayot varaqlari" kabi she'rlar to'plami bosilib chiqqan. Shoiraning umr yo'ldoshi

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vafotidan so'ng ruhiy sog'inchilar va qalb iztiroblari bilan to'la she'rlar Zulfiya ijodida jiddiy o'zgarishlar sodir bo'ldi. Uning ko'pgina she'rlarida vatanparvarlik, xalqiga bo'lgan muhabbat kabi mavzular ilgari surilgan bo'lsada, ma'yuslik ohangi bor edi. Uning hislari aks etgan she'ridan 1 parcha aytib o'tsak:

O'zing tashna etding, o'zing

suv tutding,

Qalbidagi sahrom,

daryomsan xalqim.

Seni seva-seva men boyib

ketdim,

Dunyo ichra topgan,

dunyomsan xalqim.

1940- yil oxirida e'lon qilingan davlatining san'at va adabiyot to'g'risidagi qarorlari o'zbek adabiyotiga ham katta zarar keltiradi. Bular shoira Zulfiyani ham chetlab o'tmadi. Zulfiya - badbin kayfiyatlar, pessimistik kechinmalar kuychisi sifatida tana toshlar ostida qolgan. Ammo ko'p o'tmay, o'zbek ayollar hayotini yaxshi biluvchi shoira va jurnalist sifatida dugonalari haqida she'r va publitsistik maqolalar yozib, ularni ijtimoiy faollikka chaqirdi. O'zbek shoirasi o'z ijodida bardavom davom etdi va 50- yillarning ikkinchi yarmida u Osiyo va Afrika yozuvchilarining "tinchlik va xalqaro birdamlik" shiori ostida o'tgan harakatida faol qatnashib, jahonning bir qator mamlakatlarida bo'ldi. Hindiston, Misr, Yaponiya va qo'shni respublikalarga qilgan safari shoira ijodida chuqur iz qoldirdi. Zulfiya ijodida faqatgina o'zbek hayot ko'lami bilan cheklanib qolmay, uning ijodiga xorijiy xalqlar hayoti manzaralari ham kirib keldi.

70- yillardan boshlab uning ijodidagi milliy hayot tasvirida yangi ranglar kamalagi paydo bo'ldi. "O'ylar" (1965) she'riy guldastasi bilan boshlangan voqelikni falsafiy idrok etish tamoyili "Visol" (1972), "Yillar, yillar..." (1975) she'riy kitoblarda davom etib, shoira ijodida chinakam badiiy yuksalish davri boshlanganini namoyish etdi.

Zulfiyaxonim hayotining muhim bir qismini, H. Olimjonning adabiy merosini o'rganishga bag'ishladi. U shoirning "Semurg'" yoki "Parizod va Bunyod" dostoni asosida qo'g'irchoq teatri uchun "Semurg'" pyesasi (S. Somova bilan hamkorlikda) hamda "Zaynab va Omon" operasi librettosini yozdi.

"Javharlar Neru" (1968), "Nilufar" (1971) mukofotlari, hamda Hamza nomidagi O'zbekiston davlat mukofoti (1970) laureati, Bolgariyaning "Kirill va metodiy" (1972) ordeni sovrindori o'zbek shoirasi Zulfiya Isroilova O'zbekiston respublikasi prezidenti I. A. Karimov

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nazaridan ham chetda qolmagan. Prezidentimiz aytganlaridek: " Nafaqat o'z she'rlari balki, butun hayoti bilan o'zbek ayolini manaviy qiyofasini namoyon etgan atoqli shoirimiz Zulfiyaxonimni ham ming fidoyi insonlar qatoriga qo'shgan bo'lardim", deya ta'kidladi.

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsam, Zulfiyaxonim nafaqat she'riyatda mohirona ijod qilgan, u o'z ijodi bilan bir qatorda chin o'zbek ayoli timsolini o'zida mujassamlashtirgan. Hayotning turli sinovlariga, tamal toshlariga, kuchli irodasi ila dosh bergan shoira, H. Olimjon vafotidan so'ng turmush qurmagan va yolg'iz ayol boshi bilan ikkita farzandini voyaga yetkazgan. Bugun ushbu maqolani yozish va o'zbek shoirasi Zulfiyaxonim ijodiga chuqurroq nazar solish orqali yana bir karra amin bo'ldimki, o'zbek adabiyotida XX asrda har qancha ziddiyatli, mashaqqatli va murakkab yo'lni bosib o'tgan bo'lmasin, unda bir qator tom ma'nodagi ijodkorlar yetishib chiqqan, ular orasida porloq yulduzlardan biri bu Zulfiyaxonim bo'lgan. O'zbek shoirasi bo'lmish Zulfiyaxonimga serqirra ijodkor, sadoqatli yor, irodali ayol sifatida, mukammal inson nazarida qarash mumkin.

Birinchi Prezidentimiz aytganlaridek: "uning jahon minbarlaridan yangragan she'rlari, sharq ayollarining aql-u zakosi, fazlu kamolining yorqin ifodasi sifatida millionlab she'riyat muxlislariga odamiylik, muhabbat va sadoqat kabi shaxsiyat egasi" deya ta'kidladi. Darhaqiqat, betakror shaxsiyat egasi bo'lgan Zulfiya ta'sirchan she'riyati bilan uzoq yillar mobaynida millat yoshlari qalbida sadoqat saboqlarini berishda davom etmoqda.

Zulfiya nomidagi davlat mukofoti - O'zbekiston respublikasi davlat mukofotlaridan biridir. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining " Zulfiya" nomidagi davlat mukofotini ta'sis etish to'g'risidagi takliflarni qo'llab quvvatlash to'g'risida 1999- yil 10- iyundagi farmoniga binoan ta'sis etidi. Zulfiyaning jasorati, oliyanoblighi, o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchi, kuchli sabri, samimiyligi, g'ururi va his tuyg'ulari o'quvchi qalbini larzaga soladi.

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